

ZANTHALENE®

ANTI-ITCHING, SOOTHING,
SKIN SENSITIVITY MODULATOR

CHARACTERISTICS

ZANTHALENE®	AVAILABLE DOCUMENTATION
HPLC Content of total alkylamides: 4.4 - 6.4% Form: clear solution, yellow at room temperature, opalescent at the recommended storage conditions (2-8°C for long term storage) Stability: retesting date after 1 year Level of use: 0.5 - 2% Solubility*: soluble in alcohol 95°, Propylene Glycol**, Glycerin**, Butylene Glycol, Polysoprene, C12-15 Alkyl Benzoate, Wheat Germ Oil, Paraffin Oil Aqua (water): not soluble	Botanical Certificate Method of analysis Reference Standard Declaration GMO free Safety Data Sheet Stability data Published and confidential documentation Ecocert validation

* solubility has been tested at 50 mg in 10 g of solvent (RT); ** solubility has been tested at 50 mg in 10 g of solvent at 40-50°C

Hydroxy-alpha-sanshool
CAS 83883-10-7

SAFETY DATA*

- The topical application of the Zanthalene® (at a 5% concentration in a O/W emulsion) showed good tolerability and no cutaneous sensitization in 40 healthy volunteers.¹ Based on the available data, the product could be therefore considered innocuous for the foreseen use.

FORMULATION EXAMPLES

AFTER SUN RELIEF WITH ZANTHALENE®				Formulation Advice
Hexyldecanol	2.00%	Xilogel®	0.20%	As a general rule, plant derivatives should be added to the phase the most suitable for their dissolution or dispersion. In the case of Zanthalene®, its lipophilic nature makes it suitable for emulsions and should be added to the lipophilic phase. It is anyway recommended to add Zanthalene® during the cooling down process. Zanthalene® allows the formulation of fragrance-free products thanks to its pleasant, spicy, perceivable perfumed note.
Cetearyl ethylhexanoate	3.45%	Glycerin	0.20%	
Dimethicone	0.50%	Phenoxyethanol	0.30%	
Isopropyl myristate	0.55%	Aqua / Dehydroacetic acid / Benzyl alcohol	0.80%	
Acrylates / Alkyl C10-30-Acrylate crosspolymer	0.30%	ALSO SUITABLE FOR: After sun products After shave products Lotions for mosquito bites Bodycare and after peeling After depilation Hair dyes and pre-dye treatments Anti dandruff shampoos and lotions Baby care products Lip care Mild detergents and intimate cleansers		
Aqua (water)	64.30%			
Allantoin	0.50%			
Bosexil™	0.5%			
Cetearyl ethylhexanoate	1.50%			
PEG-90 Stearate / Glyceryl Stearate	2.00%			
Zanthalene®	0.50%			
Lecithin / Tocopherol / Ascorbyl Palmitate / Citric Acid	0.10%			
Aqua (water)	10.00%			
Sodium hydroxide	0.10%			
Disodium EDTA	0.30%			
Aqua (water)	10.00%			

* All safety trials are compliant to EU regulation 1223/2009.

The ingredients described herein are offered for consideration for use in personal care products. The information provided describes historical use, ingredient activity and other information that may be relevant to their use in such products. How each ingredient would contribute to a particular product would be formulation specific. Furthermore please note that this documentation is available for various countries all over the world and hence it may contain statements not applicable to your country.

PERSONAL CARE

COSMOS

ECOCERT

SOOTHING EFFECT DURING HAIR DYING

- Twenty female volunteers^{2,3,4} were selected for their specific scalp sensitivity during hair coloration. Two areas of the scalp have been defined for the application of a 0.5% Zanthalene[®] containing lotion and a blank lotion. The hairdresser has evaluated the aspect of the scalp of the volunteers as far as concerning dandruff, visible irritation, global aspect of hair before the application of the test lotion and 90 minutes after dyeing the volunteers' hair. At 60 minutes the volunteers filled in a subjective questionnaire regarding scalp perceived discomfort. The occurrence, intensity and soothing effect of the lotions have been described by the volunteers which gave a final preference of 85% for the Zanthalene[®] solution versus the blank lotion. The global aspect of scalp and hair did not vary.

REDUCTION OF CUTANEOUS SENSITIVITY

- Two additional studies⁵ have been conducted to evaluate the soothing effect of Zanthalene[®] on cutaneous thermal sensitivity. Twelve volunteers have been trained to define their perception of cutaneous heat according to the following parameters: warmth (comfortable feeling), heat (discomfort) and pain, following to a thermal stimulus delivering a certain quantity of heat and providing a continuous reading of the temperature. Following to the first reading, a Zanthalene[®] containing emulsion (at 0.5%, 2mg/cm²) and the blank emulsion have been applied to the scapular area of the volunteers. Thermal cutaneous sensitivity measurements have been performed after product application. Zanthalene[®] resulted to decrease the "heat" perception of the trained volunteers without affecting the pain threshold.

Soothing effect of Zanthalene[®] on thermal cutaneous sensitivity

REDUCTION OF ITCH INTENSITY ON MOSQUITO BITES

- An additional assessment of the soothing and anti-itching effect⁶ of Zanthalene[®] on mosquito bites was performed on 40 healthy volunteers. They recorded the intensity of itch of at least 3 mosquito bites per arm. Globally, 67.5% of the volunteers reported an anti-itching effect of the Zanthalene[®] spray lotion compared to the blank sample.
- Further clinical trials have been performed and confirmed the same soothing effects in a variety of applications.

MECHANISM OF ACTION

- In vitro*, Zanthalene[®] has shown a strong transitory action on the neuromuscular synaptic transmission.³ The activation quickly leads to the depletion of the neurotransmitter thus blocking the transmission at synaptic level. *In vitro* evaluations³ also suggest that the action of Zanthalene[®] is mediated by voltage dependent Na⁺ channels as well as chemesthetic receptors (for the tingling sensation) as TRPV1 and TRPA1.⁷ Additionally, hydroxy- α -sansool has been found to excite neurons by a unique mechanism involving the inhibition of two-pore potassium channels.⁸

DID YOU KNOW...

- Reducing the feeling of discomfort appears to be an important source of wellness and improves the look. *Zanthoxylum bungeanum* Maxim. is a remarkable example of success in ethnopharmacology: it is a perennial plant native to China and is widely used in its country of origin as a spice (known as Sichuan Pepper or Hua jiao) to reduce the irritating properties of some foods and as a treatment for gastrointestinal pain. In the traditional medicine, the plant is also known as the "toothache tree", due to its affinity to the vague nerve much stimulated in toothache conditions. Zanthalene[®] is a patented extract⁹ for cosmetic formulations obtained by supercritical CO₂ extraction. It is Ecocert validated and it has been formulated and clinically tested in multicomponent functional topical products.^{9,10}

TRADE NAME	INCI (PCPC)	INCI (E.U.)	EC	CAS N.	INDENA CODE
Zanthalene [®]	Oleyl alcohol Zanthoxylum bungeanum Fruit Extract	Oleyl alcohol Zanthoxylum bungeanum Fruit Extract	268 - 106 - 1 310 - 094 - 8	68002 - 94 - 8 102242 - 62 - 6	36ZTT0090

1. Bruno C., "Tolerability and cutaneous sensitization study in healthy volunteers after topical application of the product", report from Urbino University, 1998. - 2. DermScan Study 99827, 2000. - 3. Guglielmini G. and Cristoni A., "Zanthoxylum alatum extract inhibits skin sensitivity", *Cosmetic & Toiletries* 7, 47, 2002. - 4. Artaria C., Maramaldi G. and Appendino G., "Sichuan pepper as a skin 'spice'", *Journal of Applied Cosmetology* 29, 87-98, 2009. - 5. DermScan studies 98333 and 98333/2, 1999. - 6. Indena, data on file. - 7. Koo J.Y. et al, "Hydroxy-alpha-sanshool activates TRPV1 and TRPA1 in sensory neurons", *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 26, 1139-1147, 2007. - 8. Bryant B. and Meziane I., "Alkylamides that produce tingling paresthesia activate tactile and thermal trigeminal neurons", *Brain Research* 842, 452-460 1999. - 9. Patent US 6,419,956/EP patent 1096944. - 9. Di Pierro F., Neri M., Bollero C., "Terapia della psoriasi - Efficacia clinica di un preparato multicomponente", *Cosmetic Technology* 12(2) 13-17, 2009. 10. Morganti P et al, "Repair activity of skin barrier by chitin-nanofibrils complexes", *SCFW Journal* 137(5), 10-26, 2011.

